

The Saga of the Damodar River[†]

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This paper summarises the work done on the monitoring of the Damodar river for five years after the flood of September, 1978 in the 50 km stretch of Durgapur-Asansol industrial belt, West Bengal and 25 km downstream. The effluents of the major industries in this belt were also monitored along with the sediments at the same sites in order to assess their impact on the river water quality. The river-bed sediments were also characterised, wherever possible. It has been established that the Damodar river, both upstream and downstream of the Durgapur barrage, is contaminated with toxic metals (Hg, As, Cr *etc.*) and toxic chemicals (phenols, NH₃, sulphide *etc.*). This is likely to pose serious health hazards in the very near future for people in the region.

THE Damodar river was known in West Bengal for a long time as the 'River of sorrow'. Every year devastating flood cast a heavy shadow on the lower valley in West Bengal, causing colossal damage.

The river originates from Chhotonagpur plateau in Bihar, crosses about 500 km through Bihar and West Bengal and joins the Hoogly river opposite Falta at a point 58 km south of Calcutta. Its tributaries are the Barakar, Jamuria, Konar and Bokaro in Bihar. The river carries lot of eroded soil, pebbles, sand *etc.* from Chhotonagpur area and poses silting problems in its lower valley region in West Bengal causing flood havoc during rainy season.

In 1948, Damodar Valley Corporation was set up at the initiative of the Government of India, and State Governments of Bihar and West Bengal. The objective was to ensure all round improvement of the Damodar Valley, and the Durgapur barrage was constructed in 1955 for water supply in the region. Two main canals from right and left banks are used for irrigation in Burdwan, Bankura, Hoogly, and Howrah districts. The left bank canal is 136 km long and meets the Hoogly river near Tribeni. The provision of water resources gave impetus to the development of industries in the region from 1960 onwards.

The river upstream flows through Bihar coal belt area. On its way it picks up waste from Sindri Fertiliser (alkali, chromate, ammonia, cyanide, phenol and naphthalenes) and Bokaro thermal power units (flyash, grease, oil *etc.*), while downstream in the 50 km stretch of Asansol-Durgapur belt, it gets pollutants from various industries.

Major industries :

The Damodar Valley from Durgapur to Asansol forms the largest industrial complex in West

Bengal and in the Eastern region. The entire industrial belt can be divided into two parts, Durgapur region and Asansol-Raniganj region.

Durgapur region : Durgapur has a population of about 0.35 million (1981 census) over an area of 160 sq. km including the industries, townships and urbanised villages in the district of Burdwan. There are more than 50 factories, producing base metals, inorganic and organic heavy chemicals, gas, urea, refractories, ceramics, batteries, heavy engineering components, machine tools *etc.* The major industries, their products, water intake and waste products *etc.* are tabulated below listed in Table 1.

Asansol-Raniganj region : The Asansol region grew up in an unplanned manner centering around the coal mines much earlier than the Durgapur area. It consists of three municipality towns, Asansol, Burnpur and Raniganj. Asansol urban area is spread over 20 sq. km with a population of 3.65 lakhs. Burnpur and Raniganj areas have population of 0.85 and 1.2 lakhs, respectively. The water intake of these three towns are 2.0, 0.35 and 0.7 mgd, respectively. The major industries causing public health concern are listed in Table 2.

Sites, sampling and analysis^{1,2,4-7} : In Durgapur the storm water drain, Tamla Nalah, carries waste effluents from most of the industries, and joins the Damodar river at a distance of 5 km from Durgapur barrage (Krishnanagar, Bankura district). The upstream river receives waste effluents from coke oven plants of D.S.P. via Singaron Nalah. In Asansol region, the river receives effluents directly from B.P.M. and I.I.S.C.O., and indirectly from the storm water drain, Nunia Nalah. Thus the Damodar river is the sink for the industrial sewage. It is also the sink for the domestic sewage in the region.

[†] Based on the invited lecture at the National Symposium on "The role of Analytical Chemistry", held at Andhra University, Waltair, August 5-7, 1985.

TABLE 1—MAJOR INDUSTRIES IN DURGAPUR

Industries	Products	Water intake/ waste water (mgd)	Waste products
Durgapur Project Ltd. (D.P.L.) ^a	Power, 75 000 MW-h (per month) Coke, 19 × 10 ⁸ MT Benzene, 26 kL Toluene, 7 kL Light oil, 1.0 MT Carbolic oil, 0.7 MT Naphthalene oil, 24 MT Anthracene oil, 39 MT Pitch, 250 MT Coal tar, 800 MT Road tar, 36 MT Coal gas, 5 × 10 ⁶ nm ³	21/3.7	Phenol, ammonia, cyanide, benzene, toluene, solvent naphtha, sulphide
Durgapur Chemicals Ltd. (D.C.L.) ^a	Sodium hydroxide, liquid chlorine, phthalic anhydride, phenol, monochlorobenzene, pentachlorophenol, hydrochloric acid	1 ^c	Mercury, hydrochloric acid, phenols
Durgapur Steel Plant (D.S.P.) ^b	Coke, 1.4 × 10 ⁸ (per year) Pig iron, 0.1 × 10 ⁸ (per year) Steel ingets, 1 × 10 ⁸ (per year) Ammonium, 57 (per year) Sulphate Crude tar, 160 (per year) Benzene, 6 000 (gal/day) Toluene 900 (gal/day) Xylene, 180 (gal/day) Solvent Naphtha, 150 (gal/day)	12.75/2.5	Ammonia, cyanide, phenols, tar, sulphide, oil and grease
Hidusthan Fertiliser Corporation Ltd. (H.F.C.) ^b	Urea, 1 000 (ton/day) Ammonia, 600 (ton/day)	2 ^c	Conc. ammonia, urea, oil and grease, arsenic, chromate

^a State (West Bengal) Government. ^b Central Government. ^c Waste water.

TABLE 2—MAJOR INDUSTRIES IN ASANSOL-RANIGANJ REGION

Industry	Products (tons)	Water intake/waste water (mgd)	Waste products
Bengal Paper Mill (B.P.M.) ^a , Raniganj	Paper 38-40 × 10 ³ (Ton/year)	12-14/10-12	Tannin, lignin, phenolic compounds, sulphide, soap foam, boiler plant ash 3 000 (kg/day)
Cycle Corporation of India, Ltd. (C.C.I.L.) ^b , Asansol	1 100 bicycles (per day)	0.2 ^c	Cyanide, chromate
Carew & Co. Ltd. ^a , Asansol	Rectified spirit 3 500 (kg/day), alcoholic liquors	0.6/0.12	Nitrate, molasses
Indian Iron and Steel Co. (I.I.S.C.O.) ^b , Burnpur	Total coke 1 × 10 ⁶ (Ton/year), steel ingot 0.6 × 10 ⁶ (Ton/year), amm. sulphate 6 000 (Ton/year), crude tar 43 000 (Ton/year), crude benzene 2 000 (kL/year)	—	Ammonia, phenols, cyanide, sulphide, tar

^a Private. ^b Central Government. ^c Waste water.

At the same time, the river remains as the major source of water supply for the entire region.

Altogether about 50 sites were selected at different points of (i) drains of the major industries, (ii) Tamla Nalah, (iii) Nunia Nalah, (iv) Durgapur barrage, (v) confluences of the Nalahs with the river and downstream and (vi) the river itself. Both water samples and sediment samples were collected at the same site, as far as practicable, and at regular intervals throughout the year for five years (excluding the rainy seasons). The river was monitored over a stretch of about 120 km from Asansol to Burdwan (up to about 60 km downstream of Durgapur barrage).

The chemical characterisation of effluent and river water samples were done in terms of the parameters, pH, NH₃, total NO₃⁻+NO₂⁻, total hardness, total dissolved solid, suspended solid, dissolved oxygen (DO), chemical oxygen demand (COD), S²⁻, CN⁻, PO₄³⁻, phenols, tannin-lignin, Hg, Cr, Zn, Pb and As. The biological parameters measured were *E. coli* and total bacteria. The sediments were analysed in terms of the parameters, NH₃, total water-soluble exchangeable cation and anion, SiO₂, mixed oxide, Na, K, Zn, Pb, As, Cr, Se, S, Cd, Mn, Co, Cu, Fe, Ni, P and V.

Standard procedures were followed for preservation, chemical treatment and analysis⁸. For elemental analysis, inductively coupled plasma emission technique was employed. Hg was estimated by flameless atomic absorption method⁹.

Water quality of the Damodar river :

The barrage water quality is evident from Table 3 where seasonal variations are also shown.

The impact of the industrial waste effluents on the Damodar river in the industrial belt is observed from some typical data in Tables 4 and 5 at selected points taking I.I.S.C.O. as the reference point. The corresponding data for sediments are indicated in the parentheses for comparison.

TABLE 3—WATER QUALITY OF THE DAMODAR RIVER AT DURGAPUR BARRAGE

Parameters	Summer	Winter
pH	7.5–8.6	7.6–8.5
Specific conductance (μ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	—	190–220
<i>E. coli</i> (Count/100 cm ³)	1 800–4 × 10 ⁵	1 × 10 ⁶
Total bacteria (Count/100 cm ³)	5.2 × 10 ⁹	2.7 × 10 ⁹
Total NH ₃	0.0–6.0	0.45–2.0
Total NO ₃ ⁻ +NO ₂ ⁻	2.9–6.4	0.15–1.5
Total hardness	79–195	77.5–114
Dissolved solid	140–480	234–275
Suspended solid	5–76	15–36
COD	10–280	23–92
DO	5.0–8.2	2.4–8.2
Sulphide	0.24–1.9	0.4–0.8
Tannin and lignin	0.0–0.9	0.0–0.6
Total phosphate	0.8–1.2	0.6–0.8
Phenol	0.006–0.12	0.0–0.002

All units except those of the first four parameters are in ppm.

Conclusion :

I.I.S.C.O., C.C.I.L., Carew & Co., B.P.M. and D.S.P. plants discharge various types of pollutants (some are non-degradable and persistent) which accumulate in Durgapur barrage water. The concentrations of these toxic pollutants in barrage water are above the permissible limits for surface water. Thus, tannin-lignin (0.9 ppm), NH₃

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TABLE 4—WATER QUALITY OF UPSTREAM DAMODAR RIVER AT DIFFERENT DISTANCES FROM I.I.S.C.O.

Parameters	16 km	26 km	30 km	40 km
pH	7.4-8.5	7.7-8.7	9.0-11.7	7.9-8.1
Sp. conductance ($\mu \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	360-420	200-400	690-1 600	230-380
<i>E. coli</i> (Count/100 cm^3)	8×10^8	$1-7 \times 10^8$	-	-
Total bacteria (Count/100 cm^3)	2×10^9	$2.2-4.6 \times 10^9$	-	-
Total NH_3 (ppm)	4.8-8.1	0.32-6.0 (88)	2.0-7.5 (90)	0.9-2.4 (100)
Total $\text{NO}_2^- + \text{NO}_3^-$	3.3-13.0	0.2-4.2	0.4-6.4	2.0-11
Total hardness	90-124	70-120	230-720	100-155
Dissolved solid	210-416	236-325	760-1 740	380-530
Suspended solid	18-32	10-18	100-120	18-260
COD	52.8-60.1	33-80 (8×10^3)	320-1 960 (1×10^4)	76-240 (1×10^4)
DO	4.8-5.6	7.2-8.0	0.6-5.1	5.5-7.2
Sulphide	0.08-0.1	0.4-0.8	0.3-3.3	1.4-1.7
Tannin lignin	-	-	5.0-80	0.7-3.0
Total phosphate	0.08-0.1	2.3-5.6	0.2-3.8	0.01-1.2
Phenols	0.06-0.08	0.09-0.14	0.2-1.3	0.006-0.03
Hg	-	0.02-0.03	0.0-0.04 (0.06)	0.01
As	-	- (5.5)	- (4.5)	- (3.0)
Cr	-	- (27.5)	- (83)	- (28)
Pb	-	- (70)	- (43.5)	- (19)
Zn	-	- (50)	- (45)	- (51)

Figures in parentheses are those for sediments in ppm. The results (except those of the first four parameters) are in ppm.

TABLE 5—WATER QUALITY OF THE DAMODAR RIVER DOWNSTREAM OF DURGAPUR BARRAGE AT DIFFERENT DISTANCES FROM I.I.S.C.O.

Parameters	55 km (Tamla Nalah confluence)	57 km	68 km	71 km
pH	7.5-8.5	7.5-8.5	8.0-8.5	8.0
Sp. conductance ($\mu \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	650	500	1 000	800
<i>E. coli</i> (Count/100 cm^3)	4×10^8	2×10^8	1×10^8	1×10^8
Total bacteria (Count/100 cm^3)	1×10^9	4×10^9	9×10^9	4×10^9
Total NH_3 (ppm)	10-40	6-19 (110)	60	18 (37)
Total $\text{NO}_2^- + \text{NO}_3^-$	10-37	10-25	26.5	17
Total hardness	90-140	80-118	50-118	115
Total dissolved solid	200-500	190-350	400-500	384
Suspended solid	70-240	10-130	40-60	132
COD	78-350	60-260 (1×10^4)	64-125	55 (1.5×10^4)
DO	2.4-4.0	2.0-6.0	2.4-4.2	3.2
Sulphide	1.5-15	0.2-10	2.5-5.0	2.9
Total phosphate	0.3-2.0	0.16-1.6	0.03-1.7	0.005
Phenol	0.02-2.0	0.06-0.08	0.01-0.08	0.06
Hg	0.04-0.08	0.01-0.05 (2.5)	0.01-0.02	0.01
As	-	- (6.0)	0.15	0.01 (8.5)
Cd	-	- (7.0)	-	- (2.5)
Cr	-	- (100)	0.06	- (22)
Pb	-	- (300)	-	- (46)
Zn	-	- (350)	-	- (12)

Figures in parentheses are those for sediments in ppm. The results (except those for the first four parameters) are in ppm.

0.5-6.0 ppm), phenol (0.006-0.14 ppm), phosphate (0.6-1.2 ppm), COD (10-230), Hg (0.001-0.002 ppm) and sulphide (0.24-1.9 ppm) present in the barrage water exceed their respective tolerance limits -, 0.5, 0.002, -, 10, 0.001, 0.5 ppm, respectively. It should be noted that the barrage water remains the source of domestic water supply for Durgapur city. The conventional water treatment methods fail to remove organic matter, phenols, and toxic metals so that these find their way into the domestic water supply. Furthermore, in the process of water treatment chlorination adds to the toxicity of water by the formation of toxic chloramines and chlorophenols on reaction with NH_3 and phenol,

respectively. Thus, the residents of the city are constantly exposed to these toxic pollutants.

On the other hand, the downstream river, i.e. beyond Durgapur barrage, is contaminated by Tamla Nalah and H.F.C. drain. The Tamla Nalah delivers a heavy pollution load to the river, phenol (0.02-2.0 ppm), NH_3 (10-40 ppm), COD (80-350 ppm), sulphide (1.5-15 ppm), Hg (0.01-0.05 ppm) etc., which are deposited in the river bed. The sediments containing these parameters in 10-100 fold excess thus act as storehouse of these pollutants and supply the pollutants continuously throughout the river course.

The above data indicate the fresh growth of pollution in the Damodar river, both upstream and downstream, after the flood of 1978 (September). If this trend continues, with the public and Government matching their indifference, the Damodar river will be a dead river by 2001 A.D. and unfit for use. In the meantime, the residents in the industrial belt as well as the villagers using downstream river water will continue to remain victims of increasing water pollution.

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